

Motivation

Bringing together the trend towards **Over The Air Software Updates (OTASU)** and **heterogeneous computing platforms** in **Mixed Criticality Cyber-Physical Systems (MCCPS)**.

Objectives

- O1:** Provide **design strategies** to tackle down safety and security (SASE) issues for MCCPS implemented on heterogeneous computing platforms (R1).
- O2:** Define **SASE contracts** outlining the main foundations, modularity and composability, to support MCCPS update continuum (R2).
- O3:** Elaborate **observability, controllability** and **feedback strategies** (R3).
- O4:** UP2DATE **software architecture** integrating: a secure communication library, and U2D middleware to support the update cycle (R4, R5, R8).

R5: UP2DATE architecture for OTASU

- O5:** UP2DATE architecture **demonstrator** applied to two case-studies: automotive and railway (R6, R7).
- O6:** **Assessment** of the future safety and security certifiability of the main UP2DATE concepts and architecture (R6, R7).
- O7:** foster **dissemination** and **technology transfer** activities.

Key UP2DATE Innovations

SASE CONTRACTS

UP2DATE defines the concepts of **vertical contracts** (hardware resource allocation requirements) and **horizontal contracts** (safety and security constraints)

UPDATE CONTINUUM

DEVOPS DEVELOPMENT

UP2DATE replaces the traditional single design phase approach with an **interactive development** process:

- Event monitors → testing with runtime checks
- Operation time data → non-functional optimization

UP2DATE Software Architecture

USE-CASE APPLICATIONS

Implementation and validation of the UP2DATE Software Architecture in the automotive and railway domain:

RAILWAY
Integrate UP2DATE architecture in a mixed-criticality gateway device that centralizes the simultaneous downloading of updates on all the railway devices

AUTOMOTIVE
Apply UP2DATE approach to update the software controlling a powertrain unit satisfying SASE requirements

- SASE Concept** – incremental strategy to define safe and secure design concepts and the required argumentation and evidences to support the future certification
- Vertical & Horizontal Contracts Model** – build around modularity (software logical and technical architecture) and composability (hierarchical application) properties
- SASE Criteria for Contracts** – integrate of safety properties (i.e., time & space independence, resource usage) and end-to-end security properties for OTASU
- UP2DATE Middleware** – implement minimum services (i.e., compatibility & integration checking, update and monitoring) to support the entire update cycle
- Secure Communication** – define and implement the security communication mechanism and library at the base of software updates
- Monitoring & Controllability** – implement monitoring services (observability and feedback) and configuration (controllability) of the HW platform to host new updates

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